

Spectrophotometric Determination of Magnesium(II) with 2-Carboxy-2'-hydroxy-3',5'-dimethylazobenzene-4- sulphonic Acid

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2-Carboxy-2'-hydroxy-3',5'-dimethylazobenzene-4-sulphonic acid (CHDMAS) is recommended as a chelating agent for the spectrophotometric determination of magnesium (II). It forms a red coloured complex with magnesium(II) which can be quantitatively determined at pH 11.0. The complex has absorption maximum at 510 nm and it obeys Beer's law over 0.5 μg to 16.0 μg Mg(II) per ml. The reagent forms 1 : 1 complex with Mg(II). The method is sensitive and fast.

SAMPLES containing large amounts of calcium and magnesium are generally analysed by classical techniques, but this is prone to errors because of coprecipitation and solubility effects¹. Careful control of pH is also essential during precipitation. Complexometric methods are also not completely satisfactory^{2,3}. However, very few methods are available for microdetermination of magnesium. The determination of trace amounts of Mg(II) is often based on lake formation or indirect photometric determination^{4,5}. Large number of dyes such as Titan Yellow⁴, curcumin, 1,2,5,8-tetrahydroxyquinone, etc. have been used for spectrophotometric determination of Mg(II). But, it is very difficult to obtain accurate and reproducible results with lake formation because of variations in dyestuff samples, precipitation of the lake, rapid fading of the colour and the uncertain effects of other metals. Eriochrome Black T has been used earlier for photometric determination of Mg(II), but most of the alkaline earth metals interfere and their prior separation is necessary⁵. Mg(II) is also determined by using 2-[2-hydroxy-3-(2,4-xylylcarbonyl)-1-naphthylazophenol and its sulphinate as photometric reagents^{6,7}. Fe³⁺, Cu²⁺ and Al³⁺ interfere seriously. Recently, Eriochrome Cyanine R is employed for the spectrophotometric determination of Mg(II)⁸. The molar absorptivity of this method is $1.90 \times 10^3 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is comparable to that of present method ($1.5 \times 10^3 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), but the colour stability of the former method is only 1 h.

2-Carboxy-2'-hydroxy-3',5'-dimethylazobenzene-4-sulphonic acid (CHDMAS) has been recently

explored as potential chelating agent for the spectrophotometric determination of large number of metal ions⁹⁻¹². Further studies of azodyes with metals in this laboratory have shown that CHDMAS can be employed for the spectrophotometric determination of Mg(II) at pH 11.0. The method is simple, rapid, sensitive and applicable at the tracer level. The advantage of the proposed method over the earlier methods is that Mg(II) can be determined in the presence of about ten fold excess of Ca(II). Other metal ions which are generally associated with Mg(II) in most of its ores and minerals are also tolerated to the sufficient extent. The method can be successfully applied for the determination of magnesium from some geological materials.

Experimental

Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer with 10 mm quartz cells and ELICO pH meter with glass and saturated calomel electrodes were used.

Magnesium sulphate (A.R.) was dissolved in double distilled water (0.05 M) and standardized¹³. The reagent CHDMAS was synthesized as reported earlier¹⁰. 0.001 M CHDMAS solution in water was used for the spectrophotometric studies. The solutions of desired concentrations were prepared by appropriate dilutions of stock solution.

A solution containing less than 160 μg magnesium and 4 ml (0.001 M) CHDMAS was adjusted to pH 11.0 with ammonium hydroxide and ammonium chloride buffer (10 ml). The absorbance of the solution was measured at 510 nm against the reagent solution as a blank.

Standard geological samples were obtained from the Geological Survey of India, Nagpur. The sample was decomposed with hydrochloric acid and the silica dehydrated by baking at low temperature. The hydrous oxides were precipitated with ammonium hydroxide, using bromine water to oxidise iron and any manganese present. Ammonium salts were destroyed by evaporation with concentrated nitric acid and residue extracted with a little dilute hydrochloric acid. The volume was made up to 250 ml with distilled water and magnesium was determined according to general procedure and reported as MgO.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra: The spectra of CHDMAS at pH 11.0 exhibit maximum at 473 nm. The absorption spectra of Mg(II)-CHDMAS complex against reagent blank exhibit a peak at 510 nm (Fig. 1).

Fig 1. Absorption spectra of reagent and complex. ○—pH 11.0, △—pH 11.3; complex against reagent blank [Mg]=[CHDMAS]= $1.6 \times 10^{-4} M$, ●—pH 11.0; reagent against water [CHDMAS]= $2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Effect of pH and CHDMAS concentration: The absorption spectra of Mg(II)-CHDMAS complex at different pH values in the pH range 9.0-12.0 indicate that the complexation starts at 9.2 and is maximum at 11.0. The absorbance decreases after pH 11.0. The Vosburgh and Cooper's method¹⁴ showed existence of only one complex at 510 nm and at pH 11.0.

The concentration of the reagent CHDMAS was varied from 0.25-10.0 times the metal ion. Maximum absorbance was obtained with 2 times excess of the reagent. The color develops immediately on addition of the reagent and the complex is stable for 24 h.

Beer's law, optimum range and molar absorptivity: It was observed that the system adhered to Beer's law in the concentration range 0.5-16.0 $\mu g ml^{-1}$ Mg(II) at 510 nm. The optimum range suitable was evaluated as 1.2 to 12.0 $\mu g ml^{-1}$ Mg(II) at 510 nm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $1.5 \times 10^5 l mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$ and $0.016 \mu g cm^{-2}$, respectively.

Composition of the complex: The stoichiometry of Mg(II) complex with CHDMAS was determined by the mole ratio¹⁵, slope ratio¹⁶ and Job's method¹⁷. The results indicate that the reagent forms 1 : 1, Mg(II) : CHDMAS complex at pH 11.0.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

[Mg] = 40 μg , [CHDMAS] = $3.4 \times 10^{-4} M$, pH 11.0

Ions	Added as	Tolerance limit, μg
Al(III)	$Al_2(SO_4)_3 \cdot (NH_4)_2 SO_4 \cdot 24H_2O$	27
Ca(II)	$CaCl_2$	400
Fe(II)	$FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$	28
Fe(III)	$Fe(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$	21
Sr(II)	$SrCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$	900
Zn(II)	$Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$	650
Oxalate	Oxalic acid	1300
Tart ²⁻	Tartaric acid	1500
PO ₄ ³⁻	KH_2PO_4	None
EDTA ⁴⁻	EDTA (Disodium salt)	1100

Effect of diverse ions: The tolerance limit was set at the amount of ion that could cause $\pm 2\%$ error in the determination of Mg(II). The results (Table 1) show that Cr(III), Zn(II), Ca(II), Sr(II), oxalate, tartrate and EDTA did not interfere. Fe(II), Fe(III) and Al(III) in trace quantity did not interfere. Phosphate interferes seriously.

Precision and accuracy: The absorbance of solution from 12 determinations of $4.0 \mu g ml^{-1}$ Mg(II) was found to be 0.240 ± 0.005 . The relative mean and standard deviations were found to be ± 0.90 and $\pm 1.08\%$, respectively.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF MAGNESIUM(II) IN GEOLOGICAL SAMPLES

Sample	MgO present %	MgO found* %
Low magnetia limestone I	1.96	2.02
Low magnetia limestone II	0.85	0.90
Dolomite	30.40	31.20
NBS No. 104, Burnt magnesite	85.67	86.40

*Average of three determinations.

The proposed method has been applied successfully to some standard geological samples and the results are summarized in Table 2.

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